

The Book of Hosea

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Entry tags: Levantine Religion, Early Christianity, Christianity, Religious Group, Biblical Prophets, Early Jewish Literature, Hebrew Bible, Text, Near East, Prophecy, Scripture, Jewish Traditions, Judeans and Israelites

The book of Hosea is one of the prophetic books of the Hebrew Bible, and the first book of the Minor Prophets as listed in the Masoretic text and the Septuagint. The book of Hosea featured prominently in the Qumran community, as three manuscripts of Hosea were found at Qumran (4Q78-79, 4Q82) as well as fragments of a "Peshier Hosea" (4Q166-167). The book contains 14 chapters, the first of which offer a narrative account of the prophet Hosea followed by poetic oracles and sayings attributed to him. Hosea was a northern prophet who, according to the superscription in 1:1, operated in the Northern Kingdom around the time leading up to its fall in 722 BCE. Although much of the book focuses on the 8th century Northern Kingdom, the book also includes references to Judah that likely reflect a later historical period. References to the nation of Judah and allusions to its fall in 586 BCE lead scholars to conclude that the book of Hosea was likely composed over a long period of time, beginning with the 8th century prophetic sayings, and continuing into the 6th century and beyond, as those words became reinterpreted for a primarily Judean exilic and post exilic audience. In reception history, the book of Hosea is most well-known for its coinage of the "marriage metaphor." In the opening chapter of the book, Yahweh commands Hosea to take Gomer, a woman of zonah, often translated "whoredom," as his wife. This troubled marriage is meant to reflect the fracturing relationship between Yahweh, the husband, and his wife, Israel. While the marriage metaphor is only loosely operative in the chapters following Hosea 1-3, later biblical authors such as Jeremiah, Ezekiel, and Paul of the New Testament take up and expand the metaphor in their later writings (Jeremiah 1-3, Ezekiel 16 and 23, Romans 9). Moreover, Jewish and Christian commentators later interpreted the relationship of the couple in the Song of Songs in light of the marriage metaphor, leading them to liken the young couple to Yahweh and Israel, or Christ and the church. In recent scholarship, the marriage metaphor has been addressed by feminist scholars who point out the issues, theologically, politically, and socially, with the way the marriage metaphor depicts woman as a stand-in for sin, infidelity, and impurity. The disturbing imagery and implications of this metaphor serve the rhetorical efforts of the prophet, who sought to emphasize the fractured nature of Israel's relationship with its god, Yahweh.

Date Range: 800 BCE - 500 BCE

Region: Northern Kingdom of Israel

Region tags: Israel

Northern Kingdom of Israel, roughly 950 - 722 BCE

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: O'Brien, Julia, ed. *Oxford Handbook of the Minor Prophets*. Oxford University Press, 2021.

– Source 2: Gruber, Mayer. Hosea: A Textual Commentary. Bloomsbury, 2017.

– Source 3: Wolff, Hans Walter. Hosea: A Commentary on the Book of the Prophet Hosea. Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1974.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: Ink on papyrus

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: The versions of the Book of Hosea at Qumran were stored in jars in caves. It is unknown if other manuscripts were stored in similar fashion.

↳ Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Besides the discovery at Qumran, the field does not know how these text would have been stored. It is possible they would have been stored in temple or other administrative buildings.

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– Field doesn't know

↳ Cave(s)

– Yes

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Field doesn't know

↳ Library/archive

– Field doesn't know

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Textual production in the ancient world is often connected to state formation and development. However, the biblical prophets are so often critical of the state that it is hard to imagine these texts were sanctioned by, or funded by the state.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: This text is considered official religious scripture by modern religious communities, but the notion of an "official religious scripture" is anachronistic to the communities who produced and first engaged with this text.

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

Notes: While prophets were believed to have been the messengers of Yahweh, the texts themselves were written by those human scribes.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

Notes: Although in modernity the text is considered "scripture" and thus unalterable, this would not have been the attitude of ancient authors and audiences. The notion of a "closed cannon" of "scripture" is a later concept not applicable to the composition or early interaction with the book of Hosea.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Scribes were likely responsible for the writing of "scripture" (again, anachronistic terminology). Scribes were trained to copy, alter, and compose texts.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– I don't know

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– No

Notes: Although the book of Hosea is now part of the Jewish and Christian scriptural canons, it was not initially part of a codified canon of scriptures. At Qumran, the book of Hosea was found on a two scrolls including other minor prophets, leading scholars to argue that the individual prophetic books may have been gathered into a collection of texts in antiquity. However, this collection would not have been considered "canon of scriptures" by those compiling the collection.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: Although Biblical Hebrew is now considered a religious or sacred language by certain communities, it likely reflected a language similar to the vernacular of the scribes and audiences of the text.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: There are slightly different versions of the book of Hosea in the Masoretic Text, the Septuagint, and at Qumran. Ancient scribes and audiences would not have been bothered by variation.

If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– I don't know

Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Notes: As referenced above, the book of Hosea was gathered into a collection of Minor Prophets but this would not have been considered "canonization."

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: The god yahweh is described with metaphors like "father" and "husband."

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - No

- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: God communicated through prophets words of judgement and salvation relating to historical-political and social circumstances.

- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes

- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes

- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
 - Notes: This is a major theme in the book of Hosea.

- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - I don't know

- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes

- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes

- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: It is a debate in the field whether or not the Israelite god Yahweh ate. This however, is not present in Hosea.

- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No

- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– No

Notes: Other prophets encounter Yahweh in dreams, but dream oracles are not present in Hosea.

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

Notes: Again, trance possession is attested in the Hebrew Bible (1 Samuel 19 for instance) this doesn't appear to occur in the book of Hosea.

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

Notes: Hosea was not a "religious specialist" per se, but he was a prophet. It is not clear the degree to which Hosea (or other writing prophets) were part of any formalized religious institution in Israel. Many of them likely operated within the "official" temple structure (whatever that may have looked like), but many did not.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Notes: The text is framed as a record of an encounter between Yahweh and the prophet, but the text itself does not give the reader any super nature power or unique connection with the divine.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

Notes: Throughout the book, Yahweh accuses the Israelite priest of performing wrong or bad sacrifices.

↳ Libations?
– No

↳ Food?
– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?
– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?
– No

↳ Sacred objects?
– No

↳ Daily life objects?
– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

Notes: Adultery serves as a guiding metaphor throughout the book. Israel's trust in other nations and other deities is cast as "adultery" against their national God, Yahweh.

↳ Incest

– No

Notes: This is not a concern in the Book of Hosea.

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– No

Notes: This is not a concern in the Book of Hosea.

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– Yes

Notes: The book of Hosea depicts a tumultuous marriage resulting in the husband, Yahweh abusing his wife, Israel to punish her for the "adultery" she committed by worshiping other gods (Hosea 1-3). Feminist scholars have critiqued this metaphor for the ways it seems to permit spousal abuse. Hosea's depiction of marriage and sex reflect its patriarchal worldview and the oppressive social conditions faced by women in the ancient world.

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - No
 - Notes: This is not a concern in the Book of Hosea.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - No
 - Notes: This is not a concern in the Book of Hosea.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
 - Notes: To the extent that the powerful abused property laws for their own advantage (Hosea 7:1-2).
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - No
 - Notes: This is not a concern in the Book of Hosea.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Notes: As a response to Israel's various sins, noted throughout the book

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: In the book of Hosea, punishment is largely caused by Israel's turning to other gods (discussed metaphorically throughout the book as "adultery" or "whoring"). By using the metaphor of adultery, Hosea indirectly attempts to uphold the social expectations of women to have one sexual partner, her husband. Hosea also accuses the political and religious elites of abusing their power, thus critiquing the political and religious institutions of Israel as well.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
– No
Notes: Punishment directed towards religious group.

↳ Consists of bad luck?
– No

↳ Political failure?
– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?
– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?
– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
– No

↳ Sickness or illness?
– No

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: The main focus on Hosea is the proper and exclusive worship of Yahweh.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– I don't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

Drama?

– Yes

Notes: Hosea 1-3 is a dramatic narrative meant to have a strong rhetorical effect. Hosea's

marriage to Gomer in addition to the vivid and dramatic names of his children serve to highlight the depravity of Israel's situation and the break in their relationship with Yahweh. While I don't know that this is meant to be "entertaining," poetic elements and dramatic storytelling are employed by the scribe to great effect.

↳ Comedy?

– No

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: The text requires proper sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of sacred space, but does not describe or specify what those proper practices are.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Since the date of composition is unknown and likely spans across many different political institutions, the most we can say is that there was a (or multiple) scribal apparatus that facilitated the production of this text.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Elite groups are thought to have controlled text production.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Book of Hosea, Gruber, Mayer. Hosea: A Textual Commentary. Bloomsbury, 2017.

Reference: The Book of Hosea, Wolff, Hans Walter. Hosea: A Commentary on the Book of the Prophet Hosea. Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1974.

Reference: The Book of Hosea, O'Brien, Julia, ed.. Oxford Handbook of the Minor Prophets. Edited by Julia O'Brien. Oxford University Press, 2021.